

What Influences Citizens' Expectations towards Digital Government? An Exploratory Survey Supplementary material

Outline

This report contains the following elements.

- Full questionnaire (page 2):** The distributed questionnaire is provided in full, in a form that makes it reusable by other researchers.
- List of variables (page 6):** All the variables measured with the questionnaire are described. For each, the name of the variable, its type, its possible values, and a textual description of what the variable measures are given.
- Generated variables (page 9):** In order to conduct the quantitative analysis, a transformation of some of the measured variables into other constructs was necessary. More precisely, a digital literacy score was computed by aggregating several measured variables.
- Data analysis (page 10):** The quantitative data analysis techniques used are detailed. In particular, the statistical tests performed for each research question are listed, and their choice justified.
- Abbreviations (page 12):** A list of the abbreviations that are used in the Results section is provided.
- Results (page 13):** The insights from the exploration of data and from the statistical tests are presented, structured according to the list of research questions. The details (i.e. statistic value and significance level) are provided for each test.

The following additional files are also provided.

- Dataset:** The data collected through the questionnaire and analyzed in this study is provided in full for any interested researcher to reuse. The dataset is provided as an Excel spreadsheet and is available at this [link](#).
- Summary** An Excel spreadsheet containing two sheets provides a table overview of all the relationships identified in this study and gives the details of all the significant statistical tests. It is available at this [link](#).

Socio-Economic Characteristics
Q13. In which age interval do you fall? <input type="radio"/> Under 20 years old <input type="radio"/> 20-29 <input type="radio"/> 30-39 <input type="radio"/> 40-49 <input type="radio"/> 50-59 <input type="radio"/> Over 60
Q14. What is your gender? <input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Male <input type="radio"/> Other
Q15. What is the highest degree you received? <input type="radio"/> No degree <input type="radio"/> Primary school degree (until 12 years old) <input type="radio"/> Inferior secondary school degree (until 15 years old) <input type="radio"/> Superior secondary school degree (until 18 years old) <input type="radio"/> High school degree <input type="radio"/> University degree <input type="radio"/> PhD
Q16. What is your current occupation? <input type="radio"/> Student <input type="radio"/> helper <input type="radio"/> Employed <input type="radio"/> Self-employed <input type="radio"/> Unemployed <input type="radio"/> Retired
<i>If answer to Q16 was [Employed]</i> Q17. Do you work in a public administration? <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes, at a local level <input type="radio"/> Yes, at a provincial level <input type="radio"/> Yes, at a regional level <input type="radio"/> Yes, at a federal level <input type="radio"/> Yes, at a European level

List of variables

Table 1: Measured variables (continued).

Variable	Type	Possible values
<i>pues_use_frequency</i>	Ordinal	never — yearly — monthly — weekly — daily
		Frequency to which the respondent uses public electronic services
<i>local_faster_integrated</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent wishes that the electronic public services of her (his) city were more accessible, faster, and more integrated with other levels of authority
<i>local_pay</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent would be willing to pay extra money (directly or through taxes) so that the electronic public services of her (his) city are more accessible, faster, and more integrated with other levels of authority
<i>local_consult</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent would take time to consult relevant information about her (his) city if they were available
<i>local_democratic</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent would take time to use an online platform to participate in the democratic processes of her (his) city if such a platform existed
<i>local_burden</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		In exchange for a greater time investment on the respondent's part, s(he) would favor the use of public services if it reduced her (his) city's administrative burden
<i>local_send</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent would take time to send relevant information to her (his) city's departments through an online platform if such a platform existed
<i>local_development</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent would take time to participate in the development of her (his) city's electronic public services if s(he) were given the opportunity
<i>federal_faster_integrated</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5)
		The respondent wishes that the electronic public services of her (his) country or region were more accessible, faster, and more integrated with other levels of authority

Table 2: Measured variables (continued).

Variable	Type	Possible values
<i>federal_pay</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) The respondent would be willing to pay extra money (directly or through taxes) so that the electronic public services of her (his) country or region are more accessible, faster, and more integrated with other levels of authority
<i>federal_consult</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) The respondent would take time to consult relevant information about her (his) country or region if they were available
<i>federal_democratic</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) The respondent would take time to use an online platform to participate in the democratic processes of her (his) country or region if such a platform existed
<i>federal_burden</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) In exchange for a greater time investment on the respondent's part, s(he) would favor the use of public services if it reduced the administrative burden of her (his) country or region
<i>federal_send</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) The respondent would take time to send relevant information to the departments of her (his) country or region through an online platform if such a platform existed
<i>federal_development</i>	Ordinal	totally disagree (1) — disagree (2) — neutral (3) — agree (4) — totally agree (5) The respondent would take time to participate in the development of the electronic public services of her (his) country or region if s(he) were given the opportunity
<i>pres_use_frequency</i>	Ordinal	never — yearly — monthly — weekly — daily Frequency to which the respondent uses private electronic services
<i>sm_use_frequency</i>	Ordinal	never — yearly — monthly — weekly — daily Frequency to which the respondent uses social media
<i>digital_literacy_tagging</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding Respondent's understanding of the <i>tagging</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_pdf</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding Respondent's understanding of the <i>PDF</i> concept

Table 3: Measured variables (continued).

Variable	Type	Possible values
<i>digital_literacy_spyware</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>spyware</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_wiki</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>wiki</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_jpg</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>JPG</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_weblog</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>weblog</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_cache</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>cache memory</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_malware</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>malware</i> concept
<i>digital_literacy_phishing</i>	Ordinal	no understanding — poor understanding — moderate understanding — good understanding — full understanding
		Respondent's understanding of the <i>phishing</i> concept
<i>age</i>	Ordinal	<20 — 20-29 — 30-39 — 40-49 — 50-59 — >60
		Respondent's age
<i>education</i>	Ordinal	none — primary — inferior secondary — superior secondary — high school — university — PhD
		Respondent's highest obtained degree
<i>gender</i>	Dichotomous	female — male (the "other" answer was not given by any respondent)
		Respondent's gender
<i>occupation</i>	Nominal	student — helper — employee — self-employed — unemployed — retired
		Respondent's current occupation
<i>occupation_administration</i>	Nominal	none — local — provincial — regional — federal — european
		Respondent's employment in a public administration, and level of authority of the administration

Generated Variables

Digital Literacy

Digital literacy is measured with an established scale comprising 9 items, each measured on a 5-point Likert scale going from “No understanding” to “Full understanding”. In order to assess the internal consistency of the scale from the data collected, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient [1] was computed and is 0.923. As the commonly accepted threshold for Cronbach’s alpha is 0.7, the digital literacy scale is considered reliable. Therefore, a digital literacy score could be obtained for each respondent by mapping each rung of the Likert scale to a number (“No understanding” was mapped to 1, “Full understanding” was mapped to 5) and computing the arithmetic mean of the nine Likert items. Thus, the digital literacy score is within the range of 1 (the respondent answered “No understanding” for the nine items) to 5 (the respondent answered “Full understanding” for the nine items). Then, the Shapiro-Wilk test was run in order to determine whether the new digital literacy score variable is normally distributed. The Shapiro-Wilk test was chosen as it was shown to be more powerful than alternative normality tests [5]. Computation returned a Shapiro-Wilk W of 0.952 (p-value = 0.000), meaning that that the digital literacy score is not normally distributed. Table 4 lists the generated variables, their type, the range of their possible values, and their definition.

Table 4: Generated variables.

Variable	Type	Possible values
<i>digital_literacy</i>	Continuous	From 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest), computed as the arithmetic mean of the 9 questionnaire items
		Digital literacy measured according to [2,4,3]

Data Analysis

Due to all variables being either non continuous or not normally distributed, only non-parametric tests were used. Table 5 details the tests used, for each independent–dependent variable type combination. In this study, all dependent variables are of ordinal type.

Table 5: Statistical test according to independent and dependent variable type

Independent — dependent variable type	Statistical test
Dichotomous — Ordinal	The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to compare the distribution of the dependent variable across the two groups defined by the independent variable (e.g. the distribution of answers given to S1 across males and females). If the test reveals a significant difference, visually examining the distributions allow determining the direction of the difference.
Nominal (more than 2 groups) — Ordinal	The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to compare the distribution of the dependent variable across the groups defined by the independent variable (e.g. the distribution of answers given to S1 across occupation groups). If the test reveals a significant difference, a post-hoc analysis with Dunn’s test (with Bonferroni correction) can be performed to determine if there are pairwise differences across the groups.
Ordinal — Ordinal	The Jonckheere-Terpstra test was used to determine whether there is significant trend between the independent and the dependent variable. An example of such trend would be that citizens with higher degrees tend to agree more with one given statement. If the test reveals a significant difference, a post-hoc analysis with Dunn’s test (with Bonferroni correction) can be performed to determine if there are pairwise differences across the groups.
Continuous — Ordinal	The Jonckheere-Terpstra test was used to to determine whether there is significant trend between the dependent and the independent variable. For example, the test compares the distribution of digital literacy across the five groups defined by the five possible answers to S1 to determine whether respondents agreeing more with the statement tend to have a higher or lower digital literacy. If the test reveals a significant difference, a post-hoc analysis with Dunn’s test (with Bonferroni correction) was performed to determine if there are pairwise differences across the groups.

As for RQ1 (government level), the answers given for the local and for the regional/federal government levels were compared pairwise, for each of the seven

statements relating to the citizens' roles, in order to determine whether they tend to be similar. As ordinal variables are involved in RQ1, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient [7] was used and interpreted following [6].

Table 6 summarizes the statistical tests performed for each research question.

Table 6: Research questions with associated variables and statistical tests.

Research question	Variables involved	Statistical tests
RQ1 (government level)	<i>local_* — federal_*</i>	Spearman's correlation
RQ2a (gender)	<i>gender — local_* — federal_*</i>	Kolmogorov-Smirnov
RQ2b (age)	<i>age — local_* — federal_*</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ2c (education level)	<i>education — local_* — federal_*</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ2d (occupation)	<i>occupation — local_* — federal_*</i>	Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ2e (administration)	<i>occupation_administration — local_* — federal_*</i>	Kolmogorov-Smirnov
RQ3 (digital literacy)	<i>digital_literacy — local_* — federal_*</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ4a (private e-service use frequency)	<i>pres_use_frequency</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ4b (social media use frequency)	<i>sm_use_frequency — local_* — federal_*</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis
RQ4c (public e-service use frequency)	<i>pues_use_frequency — local_* — federal_*</i>	Jonckheere-Terpstra with Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis

* is a wildcard and is used to represent the set of all variables matching the pattern it describes (e.g. *local_** represents the seven variables starting by *local_*)

All statistical tests were run on the IBM SPSS software (version 26).

Abbreviations

Table 7 lists the abbreviations that are used to detail the results in the next section.

Table 7: Abbreviations.

Abbreviation	Meaning
loc	local government level
fed	federal/regional government level
p	p-value
r_s	Spearman's correlation coefficient
K-S	Kolmogorov-Smirnov test statistic
J	Jonckheere-Terpstra test statistic
H	Kruskal-Wallis test statistic
Z	Dunn test statistic (post-hoc analysis)
TD	Group of respondents who answered "Totally disagree" to the statement
D	Group of respondents who answered "Disagree" to the statement
N	Group of respondents who answered "Neutral" to the statement
A	Group of respondents who answered "Agree" to the statement
TA	Group of respondents who answered "Totally agree" to the statement

Results

Sample Description

Gender In total, 92 (45.32%) females and 111 (54.68%) males completed the questionnaire (Figure 1, page 13).

Fig. 1: Distribution of the respondents according to gender.

Age The median age of the respondents is between 30–39. The most represented age group is 20-29, with 81 (39.90%) respondents. Each group contains 21 respondents or more (Figure 2, page 14).

Education Level The education levels reported by the Belgian government census are *low*, *medium*, and *high*. Low corresponds to an inferior secondary degree at maximum, medium to the superior secondary degree, and high to any degree higher than superior secondary (i.e. high school, university, PhD). Most of the respondents (127, 62.56%) have a higher education degree and therefore fall into the high level. 69 respondents (34%) fall into the medium level, and the remaining 7 (3.4%) into the low level (Figure 3, page 14).

Occupation The sample is mostly composed of employees (99 respondents, 48.77%) and students (67 respondents, 33%). 14 respondents (6.90%) are self-employed, 6 (2.96%) are unemployed, 16 (7.88%) are retired, and 1 (0.49%) is a homemaker (Figure 4, page 15).

Fig. 2: Distribution of the respondents per age group.

Fig. 3: Distribution of the respondents per education level.

Fig. 4: Distribution of the respondents per occupation.

Digital Literacy Digital literacy is measured on a continuous scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 corresponding to the lowest digital literacy level, and 5 to the highest. Overall, respondents are evenly distributed along the scale, except for the maximal value of the score, which was reached by 22 (10.84%) respondents. A notable difference can be observed between males and females (Figure 5, page 16). Females tend to achieve a lower score than males.

Private Electronic Service Use 45 (22.17%) respondents use private electronic services on a daily basis and 102 (50.25%) use them weekly. 37 (18.23%) respondents use private electronic services monthly. 19 (9.36%) respondents use them more rarely, including 10 not using them altogether (Figure 6, page 16).

Social Media Use 157 (77.34%) respondents use social media on a daily basis and 14 (6.90%) use them weekly. 10 (4.93%) respondents use social media monthly. 22 (10.84%) respondents use them more rarely, including 20 not using them altogether (Figure 7, page 17).

Public Electronic Service Use 55 (27.09%) respondents never use public electronic services. 116 (57.14%) use them on a yearly basis and 24 (12.32%) use them monthly. 8 (3.94%) respondents use public electronic services more frequently (Figure 8, page 17).

RQ1: Does the *level of government* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

First, a bubble chart of the responses was built for each of the seven statements related to local and federal/regional government levels. The chart contains one

Fig. 5: Distribution of the digital literacy score, for female and male respondents.

Fig. 6: Private electronic service use frequency by the respondents.

Fig. 7: Social media use frequency by the respondents.

Fig. 8: Public electronic service use frequency by the respondents.

bubble per possible local—regional/federal answer combination and the number of respondents whose answers match with a combination determines the area of the corresponding bubble. The bubble charts presented in Figure 9 (page 19) suggest that there is a strong positive relationship between the local and the federal/regional level, for the answers to the seven statements. Thus, it appears that respondents give highly similar answers for both government levels. In order to confirm this observation, the pairwise Spearman’s correlation coefficient were computed, for each of the seven statements. The results are reported in Table 8 (page 18).

Table 8: Pairwise Spearman’s correlation coefficient, for the seven statements on citizens’ expectations.

Statement	Pairwise correlation	Significance level
Electronic public services that are more accessible, faster and more integrated with other levels of authority	$r_S = 0.727$	0.000
Willing to pay extra money (directly or through taxes) so that electronic public services are more accessible, faster, and more integrated with other levels of authority	$r_S = 0.753$	0.000
Take time to consult relevant information if they were available	$r_S = 0.753$	0.000
Take time to use an online platform to participate in the democratic processes	$r_S = 0.713$	0.000
In exchange of a greater time investment, favor the use of public electronic service to reduce the administrative burden	$r_S = 0.741$	0.000
Take time to send relevant information through an online platform if such a platform existed	$r_S = 0.685$	0.000
Take time to participate in the development of public electronic services if given the opportunity	$r_S = 0.782$	0.000

RQ2a: Does *gender* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

Results are reported in Table 9 (page 24). For each test, the null hypothesis is that the distribution is the same for both the female and male group.

RQ2b: Does *age* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

Results are reported in Table 10 (page 37).

(a) Wish for faster and more integrated (S1)

(b) Pay for faster and more integrated

(c) Consult information

(d) Participate in democratic processes

(e) Reduce administrative burden

(f) Send information

(g) Participate in development

Fig. 9: Bubble charts representing the local (x axis)—regional/federal (y axis) answer combinations and their corresponding number of respondents.

Fig. 10: Answers distribution for *local_faster_integrated*. The distribution is given for both the female (left) and the male (right) group.

Fig. 11: Answers distribution for *federal_faster_integrated*. The distribution is given for both the female (left) and the male (right) group.

Fig. 12: Answers distribution for *local_democratic*. The distribution is given for both the female (left) and the male (right) group.

Fig. 13: Answers distribution for *federal_democratic*. The distribution is given for both the female (left) and the male (right) group.

Fig. 14: Answers distribution for *local_burden*. The distribution is given for both the female (left) and the male (right) group.

Fig. 15: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_pay*, according to the age groups.

Fig.16: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_pay*, according to the age groups.

Fig.17: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_democratic*, according to the age groups.

Fig.18: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*, according to the age groups.

Fig.19: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_burden*, according to the age groups.

Table 9: Significant results for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test measuring the influence of gender on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distributions
S1 (better public e-services) – loc	K-S = 1.702, p = 0.006	Figure 10 (page 20)
S1 (better public e-services) – fed	K-S = 1.497, p = 0.023	Figure 11 (page 20)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc	K-S = 1.809, p = 0.003	Figure 12 (page 20)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed	K-S = 1.388, p = 0.042	Figure 13 (page 20)
S5 (reduce burden) – loc	K-S = 1.367, p = 0.048	Figure 14 (page 21)

RQ2c: Does the *education level* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

The data analysis showed no influence of the education level on any of the seven statements.

RQ2d: Does *occupation* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

Only 1 of the respondents has the *helper* occupation, and 6 of them are *unemployed*. As these numbers are too low to study these two groups, they were sidelined from the analysis. Thus, the resulting sample holds 196 respondents divided among four occupation groups, namely *student*, *employed*, *self-employed*, and *retired*. Results are reported in Table 11 (page 42). For each test, the null hypothesis is that the distribution is the same across occupation groups.

RQ2e: Does *working in an administration* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

Due to small sample sizes, RQ2e was answered by studying the impact of working on an administration, regardless of the level. The group of 37 respondents working in an administration was compared to the group composed of the other 62 employed respondents.

The data analysis showed no influence of being employed by an administration on any of the seven statements.

RQ3: Does *digital literacy* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

The results are reported in Table 12 (page 43).

RQ4a: Does the use frequency of *private electronic services* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

The results are reported in Table 13 (page 44).

Fig.20: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_consult*, according to the occupation.

Fig.21: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_consult*, according to the occupation.

Fig.22: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_democratic*, according to the occupation.

Fig.23: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*, according to the occupation.

Fig. 24: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_faster*.

Fig. 25: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_faster*.

Fig. 26: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_pay*.

Fig. 27: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_consult*.

Fig. 28: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_consult*.

Fig. 29: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_democratic*.

Fig. 30: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*.

Fig. 31: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_burden*.

Fig. 32: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_send*.

Fig. 33: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_send*.

Fig. 34: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *local_development*.

Fig. 35: Distribution of the digital literacy score, according to the answers given to the statement related to *federal_development*.

Fig. 36: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_faster*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig. 37: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_faster*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig. 38: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_consult*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig. 39: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_consult*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig. 40: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig. 41: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_send*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig.42: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_send*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig.43: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_development*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Table 10: Significant results of the Jonckheere-Terpstra test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of age on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S2 (pay for better e-services) – loc Significant pairwise differences: 50-59 — 20-29 (Z = 613.000, p : 0.030)	J = 6620.000, p = 0.003	Figure 15 (page 21)
S2 (pay for better e-services) – fed Significant pairwise differences: 50-59 — 20-29 (Z = 569.000, p = 0.009)	J = 6409.000, p = 0.001	Figure 16 (page 22)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc Significant pairwise differences: >60 — 20-29 (Z = 532.500, p = 0.040) ; 40-49 — 20-29 (Z = 815.500, p = 0.038)	J = 6640.000, p = 0.004	Figure 17 (page 22)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: >60 — 20-29 (Z = 427.500, p = 0.001) ; 40-49 — 20-29 (Z = 708.000, p = 0.002)	J = 6506.500, p = 0.001	Figure 18 (page 23)
S5 (reduce burden) – fed Significant pairwise differences: 40-49 — 20-29 (Z = 808.000, p = 0.036)	J = 7017.500, p = 0.048	Figure 19 (page 23)

RQ4b: Does the use frequency of *social media* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

The results are reported in Table 14 (page 45).

RQ4c: Does the use frequency of *public electronic services* impact the roles citizens are willing to take in digital government?

The results are reported in Table 15 (page 45).

References

1. L. J. Cronbach. Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *psychometrika*, 16(3):297–334, 1951.
2. E. Hargittai. Survey measures of web-oriented digital literacy. *Social science computer review*, 23(3):371–379, 2005.
3. E. Hargittai. An update on survey measures of web-oriented digital literacy. *Social science computer review*, 27(1):130–137, 2009.
4. E. Hargittai and Y. P. Hsieh. Succinct survey measures of web-use skills. *Social Science Computer Review*, 30(1):95–107, 2012.
5. N. M. Razali, Y. B. Wah, et al. Power comparisons of shapiro-wilk, kolmogorov-smirnov, lilliefors and anderson-darling tests. *Journal of Statistical Modeling and Analytics*, 2(1):21–33, 2011.
6. P. Schober, C. Boer, and L. A. Schwarte. Correlation coefficients: appropriate use and interpretation. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 126(5):1763–1768, 2018.
7. C. Spearman. The proof and measurement of association between two things. 1961.

Fig.44: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_development*, according to the private e-service use frequency.

Fig.45: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_faster_integrated*, according to the social media use frequency.

Fig.46: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_faster_integrated*, according to the social media use frequency.

Fig.47: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_democratic*, according to the social media use frequency.

Fig.48: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*, according to the social media use frequency.

Fig.49: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_faster*, according to the public e-service use frequency.

Fig. 50: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *local_democratic*, according to the public e-service use frequency.

Fig. 51: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_democratic*, according to the public e-service use frequency.

Table 11: Significant results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of occupation on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S3 (consult information) – loc Significant pairwise differences: self-student — employed ($Z = 24.321$, std. $Z = 2.892$, $p = 0.023$) ; self-student — self-employed ($Z = 51.162$, std. $Z = 3.275$, $p = 0.006$)	$H = 14.636$, $p = 0.002$	Figure 20 (page 25)
S3 (consult information) – fed Significant pairwise differences: none	$H = 10.771$, $p = 0.013$	Figure 21 (page 25)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc Significant pairwise differences: retired — employed ($Z = 40.594$, std. $Z = 2.812$, $p = 0.030$) ; retired — self-student ($Z = -48.654$, std. $Z = -3.264$, $p = 0.007$) ; retired — self-employed ($Z = -53.223$, std. $Z = -2.715$, $p = 0.040$)	$H = 11.475$, $p = 0.009$	Figure 22 (page 26)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: retired — employed ($Z = 41.507$, std. $Z = 2.896$, $p = 0.023$) ; retired — self-student ($Z = -54.070$, std. $Z = -3.654$, $p = 0.002$)	$H = 13.427$, $p = 0.004$	Figure 23 (page 26)

Fig. 52: Distribution of the answers given to the statement related to *federal_development*, according to the public e-service use frequency.

Table 12: Significant results of the Jonckheere-Terpstra test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of digital literacy on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S1 (better e-services) – loc Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 380.000$, $p = 0.012$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1778.000$, $p = 0.001$) ; A — TA ($Z = 4679.000$, $p = 0.000$)	$J = 9206.500$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 24 (page 27)
S1 (better e-services) – fed Significant pairwise differences: TD — N ($Z = 101.500$, $p = 0.047$) ; TD — A ($Z = 313.000$, $p = 0.023$) ; TD — TA ($Z = 325.500$, $p = 0.006$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1690.000$, $p = 0.002$) ; A — TA ($Z = 5063.000$, $p = 0.000$)	$J = 9218.500$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 25 (page 27)
S2 (pay for better e-services) – loc Significant pairwise differences: D — A ($Z = 878.000$, $p = 0.010$) ; D — N ($Z = 1369.500$, $p = 0.004$)	$J = 8055.000$, $p = 0.029$	Figure 26 (page 28)
S3 (consult information) – loc Significant pairwise differences: A — TA ($Z = 2930.500$, $p = 0.018$)	$J = 8328.500$, $p = 0.007$	Figure 27 (page 28)
S3 (consult information) – fed Significant pairwise differences: A — TA ($Z = 3062.000$, $p = 0.020$)	$J = 8079.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 28 (page 29)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 495.500$, $p = 0.001$) ; D — TA ($Z = 719.000$, $p = 0.000$) ; A — TA ($Z = 3612.500$, $p = 0.000$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1254.500$, $p = 0.016$)	$J = 9655.500$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 29 (page 29)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: D — TA ($Z = 550.000$, $p = 0.000$) ; TD — TA ($Z = 481.000$, $p = 0.027$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1024.500$, $p = 0.041$) ; A — TA ($Z = 2912.000$, $p = 0.011$)	$J = 9192.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 30 (page 30)
S5 (reduce burden) – fed Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 8706.500$, $p = 0.032$	Figure 31 (page 30)
S6 (send information) – loc Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 398.500$, $p = 0.038$) ; D — TA ($Z = 523.500$, $p = 0.035$) ; A — TA ($Z = 4381.500$, $p = 0.001$)	$J = 8344.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 32 (page 31)
S6 (send information) – fed Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 188.500$, $p = 0.017$) ; D — TA ($Z = 483.000$, $p = 0.005$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1168.500$, $p = 0.002$) ; A — TA ($Z = 3376.000$, $p = 0.020$)	$J = 8763.500$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 33 (page 31)
S7 (participate in development) – loc Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 293.500$, $p = 0.002$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1498.500$, $p = 0.000$) ; D — TA ($Z = 669.000$, $p = 0.000$) ; A — TA ($Z = 1963.500$, $p = 0.000$)	$J = 9856.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 34 (page 32)
S7 (participate in development) – fed Significant pairwise differences: TD — TA ($Z = 195.000$, $p = 0.016$) ; N — TA ($Z = 1188.500$, $p = 0.000$) ; D — TA ($Z = 457.000$, $p = 0.008$) ; A — TA ($Z = 1605.500$, $p = 0.004$)	$J = 9180.500$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 35 (page 32)

Table 13: Significant results of the Jonckheere-Terpstra test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of private e-service use frequency on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S1 (better e-services) – loc Significant pairwise differences: yearly — weekly ($Z = 741.000$, $p = 0.005$) ; yearly — daily ($Z = 352.500$, $p = 0.001$) ; never — weekly ($Z = 800.500$, $p = 0.007$) ; never — daily ($Z = 378.000$, $p = 0.001$)	$J = 8661.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 36 (page 33)
S1 (better e-services) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — weekly ($Z = 838.000$, $p = 0.002$) ; never — monthly ($Z = 298.500$, $p = 0.010$) ; never — daily ($Z = 394.000$, $p = 0.000$)	$J = 8122.500$, $p = 0.001$	Figure 37 (page 33)
S3 (consult information) – loc Significant pairwise differences: never — weekly ($Z = 750.500$, $p = 0.045$) ; never — monthly ($Z = 281.000$, $p = 0.046$) ; never — daily ($Z = 368.500$, $p = 0.004$) ; weekly — daily ($Z = 2952.500$, $p = 0.015$)	$J = 7959.000$, $p = 0.006$	Figure 38 (page 34)
S3 (consult information) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — daily ($Z = 362.000$, $p = 0.006$) ; weekly — daily ($Z = 2905.000$, $p = 0.021$)	$J = 8042.500$, $p = 0.002$	Figure 39 (page 34)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — weekly ($Z = 899.000$, $p = 0.000$) ; never — daily ($Z = 396.000$, $p = 0.001$) ; never — monthly ($Z = 335.500$, $p = 0.000$)	$J = 7662.000$, $p = 0.041$	Figure 40 (page 35)
S6 (send information) – loc Significant pairwise differences: never — monthly ($Z = 302.000$, $p = 0.004$) ; never — weekly ($Z = 837.500$, $p = 0.001$) ; never — daily ($Z = 389.500$, $p = 0.001$)	$J = 8337.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 41 (page 35)
S6 (send information) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — daily ($Z = 373.000$, $p = 0.002$) ; weekly — daily ($Z = 3020.500$, $p = 0.004$)	$J = 8332.000$, $p = 0.000$	Figure 42 (page 36)
S7 (participate in development) – loc Significant pairwise differences: never — monthly ($Z = 294.500$, $p = 0.015$) ; never — weekly ($Z = 825.000$, $p = 0.004$) ; never — daily ($Z = 367.000$, $p = 0.007$)	$J = 8164.500$, $p = 0.002$	Figure 43 (page 36)
S7 (participate in development) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — weekly ($Z = 842.500$, $p = 0.002$) ; never — daily ($Z = 362.000$, $p = 0.010$) ; never — monthly ($Z = 319.500$, $p = 0.001$)	$J = 7764.500$, $p = 0.024$	Figure 44 (page 38)

Table 14: Significant results of the Jonckheere-Terpstra test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of social media use frequency on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S1 (better e-services) – loc Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 4792.000, p = 0.012$	Figure 45 (page 38)
S1 (better e-services) – fed Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 4635.500, p = 0.040$	Figure 46 (page 39)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 4819.500, p = 0.010$	Figure 47 (page 39)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — daily ($Z = 2232.500, p = 0.006$)	$J = 4996.500, p = 0.002$	Figure 48 (page 40)

Table 15: Significant results of the Jonckheere-Terpstra test and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc analysis measuring the influence of public e-service use frequency on citizens' expectations.

Statement	Statistic value and significance level	Distribution
S1 (better e-services) – fed Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 7033.500, p = 0.012$	Figure 49 (page 40)
S4 (democratic processes) – loc Significant pairwise differences: daily — monthly ($Z = 11.500, p = 0.049$) ; never — monthly ($Z = 903.500, p = 0.030$) ; never — weekly ($Z = 196.000, p = 0.034$) ; yearly — weekly ($Z = 404.000, p = 0.037$)	$J = 7116.000, p = 0.007$	Figure 50 (page 41)
S4 (democratic processes) – fed Significant pairwise differences: never — weekly ($Z = 198.000, p = 0.029$) ; yearly — weekly ($Z = 420.000, p = 0.015$)	$J = 7142.000, p = 0.006$	Figure 51 (page 41)
S7 (participate in development) – fed Significant pairwise differences: none	$J = 6890.500, p = 0.035$	Figure 52 (page 42)